

30

Developing and Analyzing Portal Based Knowledge Management Solution

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ABSTRACT

The core business data in a writing department chiefly comes from people that are concerned within the business processes. The cliquishness of information will facilitate a private to induce a far better much more robust improved} position or better role within the department. Owing to that, these people tend to not share what they recognize so as to safeguard their thus known as personal plus. Up to date, there are still no accessible tools or platform that has been developed to change data sharing within the several business. Therefore, this study is conducted to spot and manage the data exists. A data Audit was being conducted in one in every of the largest business organization to higher perceive the present scenario of information flows, possession and sharing strategies. A take a look at image of a data portal was developed because the tool for managing the structure data and as a medium to transfer the data possession from a private to organization's intellectual assets. The portal has the potential to supply data sharing, data references and most significantly the individual that has the data is cur-

rently being acknowledged. The portal was developed mistreatment Active Server Pages (ASP) because the programming script. The methodology to develop the system was supported the APQC's roadmap. Few management methods to charge data management were planned within the ending of the analysis part. The methods that are arranged out may be used as steerage for achieving a more practical data management surroundings in a very business organization.

INTRODUCTION

The publishing industry produces a variety of publications, including magazines, books, newspapers, and directories.

Various kinds of knowledge might be shared between one to another to create a knowledge sharing environment in a company. The more they share, the more successful the company will be. The knowledge that can be classified as knowledge assets for a company is very dependent to their knowledge worker might be lost if the worker leaves the company. As the result, the companies lost the most valuable assets and keep repeating the collection process every time.

Origin of the research problem

The majority of the knowledge within an Journal Editorial Department of a publishing industry belongs to the individual employees and is seldom shared throughout the organization. By being a specialist in certain area, they might have a better position and good influence in the company. Many workflows and content management system has been developed for a publishing industry, but none of them have a knowledge sharing based, to encourage people from this industry to shift the paradigm of "knowledge is owned by individuals" to the new paradigm that the knowledge is belong to the organizations.

When somebody leaves the organization, the knowledge resides in him will be gone too. The main problems the journals will face when this occurs are:-

1. Loss of external business contacts that have been established by the respective staff.

2. Loss of best practices approach those have been used by the staff in dealing with his external business contacts.

Objectives

The objectives of this study were:

(i) To conduct a knowledge audit in the editorial department to identify who has what kind of knowledge.

(ii) To develop and test a prototype portal that support knowledge management.

LITERATURE REVIEW

What is Knowledge?

Webster (1961) characterizes knowledge as an acceptable and certain discernment of something – the demonstration, the reality, or the state of understanding (ward and Holtham, 2000) Knowledge includes both knowing how, which is by and large more implied knowledge, and thinking about, which is more express knowledge (Grant, 1996). Anyway in the meantime, data ought to be recognized as building pieces of knowledge which thus is utilized for production of knowledge within the authoritative lives.

Sources of Knowledge

Davenport and Prusak (1998) recommend five sorts of knowledge that relate to the wellspring of each:

- Acquired knowledge originates from outside the association.
- Dedicated assets are those in which an association puts aside some staff parts or a whole office (typically innovative work) to create inside the foundation for a particular reason.
- Fusion is knowledge made by uniting individuals with alternate points of view to chip away at the same venture.
- Adaptation is knowledge that comes about because of reacting to new methodologies or advances in the commercial center.

Knowledge systems administration is knowledge in which individuals offer data with each one in turn formally.

Part of Knowledge Management Procedure Hierarchical Knowledge Holdings

Hierarchical knowledge holdings The authoritative isolation proposed in the past segment recommends the accompanying part possessions of hierarchical knowledge (chung, Haney and Mark 2008):

- Knowledge as encounters, mastery of people and gatherings;
- Knowledge of association that invades its processing architectures including knowledge accumulated from suppliers and associates; knowledge implanted in the IT frameworks and related information warehouses and knowledge bases;
- Knowledge with respect to clients; and
- Knowledge imparted in a worldwide undertaking.

KM Technique

Knowledge management is a situated of exercises that helps a firm to gain knowledge from both inside and outside of the organization. Associations hope to use the data gave through KM to help them perform their missions. The above viewpoints enrich KM with a key characteristic, i.e. KM is a situated of authoritative courses of action pointed at attaining particular hierarchical purposes. Through numerous research endeavors, these discoveries demonstrate that it is proper to view KM as an organization vital device. Despite the fact that we have not yet seen numerous researchers expressly group KM method and connection KM system with the current writing of corporate methods, we think it is reasonable to gather KM technique from watching the KM exercises an organization conducts (Zack, 1999).

METHODOLOGY

The methodology explains about the methodology uses for the whole study phase.

Basically the methodology used was adopting from APQC's roadmap, in order to establishing the right knowledge management strategies. APQC's Road Map to Knowledge Management Results: Stages of Implementation

Based on APQC's study of and collaboration with best practice organizations over a period of years, APQC's Road Map to Knowledge Management Results: Stages of Implementation™ framework spells out the essential steps to achieve true knowledge management implementation.

APQC's Road Map to Knowledge Management Results: Stages of Implementation™

Figure: APQC's Roadmap to Knowledge Management Results: Stages of Implementation. (Source: <http://www.apqc.com>)

SYSTEM DESIGN

Knowledge portal is a knowledge base which permits us to impart data to workers, clients and accomplices. A completely offered knowledge base that joins effective WYSIWYG altering with simple to utilize usefulness. Extraordinary outline and workflow empowers us to make and endorse articles and documents in the recent past they are made accessible to different clients. The different Record characteristic implies that our current documentation could be effortlessly embedded and it could be coordinated into our organization intranet or web. Some of its characteristics include

- ü Repeatable, reusable substance through formats, record connections and classes.
 - ü Knowledge portal is exceptionally adaptable.
 - ü Full control of clients, what they can do, and what they can see.
 - ü Could be designed to work in just about any dialect.
 - ü Reports that give facts on clients and articles
- Knowledge portal navigation gives us quick access to:
- ü Articles - read articles in the knowledgebase
 - ü Files - view attached files
 - ü News - read announcements
 - ü Email notifications - users can be notified when an item is changed.

IMPLIMENTATION AND TESTING

Knowledge Portal Overview

Knowledge portal web site www.eknowledgecell.net was developed with aim to impart 'anytime anywhere' knowledge to learners.

Home Page

This portal has features of registration, login for teachers and students. Administrator manages the portal. Other features include online communication

Figure Viewing the Online Members Other features of portal include profile management of faculties and learners, Quick Communication through Online contact and SMS. Facilitation of uploading and downloading of documents, audio and video files. Forum management of various groups on this different topic is conceptualized.

Figure 6.6 SMS,/Upload/Download/Discussion Forum

The portal is also designed to conduct surveys from various entities viz faculties, students and other stake holders.

SURVEY

Following figure shows the Survey Page DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Innovations harshly connect to four fundamental phases of the Knowledge life cycle:

1. Knowledge is procured or caught utilizing intranets, extranets, groupware, web conferencing and archive management frameworks.
2. An organizational memory is shaped by refining, sorting out, and putting away knowledge utilizing organized vaults, for example, information warehouses.

3. Knowledge is conveyed through education, preparing studys, computerized knowledge based frameworks, master systems.

4. Knowledge is connected or leveraged for further learning and development through mining of the organizational memory and the provision of master frameworks, for example, choice help supportive networks.

These stages are upgraded by successful workflow and task management.

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